

MATHEMATICS

USING TEST TASKS TO INCORPORATE NEW KNOWLEDGE AND METHODS OF ACTION INTO THE PAST EXPERIENCE OF STUDENTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Ibrahimov F.

Professor, Sheki branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0775-1048>

Karimova S.

Senior lecturer of the Sheki branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3317-4215>

Abstract

The article draws attention to the importance of using test tasks in incorporating new knowledge and methods of activity into the past experience of students in secondary schools. Examples of systematized versions of test tasks applied with the aim of developing students' knowledge, skills and habits, studying the level of development in this direction and implementing the process of strengthening with variable rules are given.

The research paper presents a summary of the psycho-didactic requirements that must be considered when selecting test tasks as a means of organizing the learning activities of students in general education schools, especially their independent work.

Keywords: actualization of past experience; subsystem; test; independent work; psycho-didactic requirements; analytical and heuristic activity; structure.

Relevance of the topic. The lack of clarity of psycho-didactic requirements that must be observed when formulating test tasks as a means of organizing the learning activities of students in general education schools, especially their independent work, negatively affects the activities of practitioners, leading to errors in the selection and application of the aforementioned training tools adequate to specific conditions. Based on this reason, we conclude that the research topic is relevant.

Methodological basis of the study. In the process of conducting the research, the "System-structural approach", which originated from L. Bertalanfi's idea of "System Analysis" [3;8] and was formed as an important branch of dialectics and rose to the level of its alternative, scientific-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal relationships of the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used as a methodological basis.

Interpretation of research materials. "One of the main and fundamental issues in modern educational theory is the problem of the structure of the process of knowledge acquisition and its dependence on what. Many studies have revealed and proven that this depends on the logical structure of the educational process itself" [1;128]. In the course of our research, which has been conducted for many years, the psycho-didactic, philosophical-methodological and logical foundations of action projects that proceed in accordance with the paths of knowledge and methods of action that have a special place in human experience and are included in the perfect learning system as subsystems have been formed. In our opinion, while in the "explanatory-reproductive subsystem" knowledge and methods of action are mainly presented to students in general education schools by the teacher, in the "subsystem based on problem-based learning" students acquire them through independent search. Since the subsystems in question

belong to the same system, the didactic system in both cases (if we do not take into account the degree of activity of the teacher and the student) is the same (the internal and methodological substructures in the organization of these subsystems differ from each other). Thus, past experience is actualized, new knowledge and methods of action are learned, and finally, they are strengthened by incorporating them into past experience. (For more detailed information, see: [11-12]) In both subsystems, the application of tests is useful in actualizing the past experience of students and incorporating new knowledge (or methods of action) into their current experience. Because the use of tests creates favorable conditions for independent work of students in accordance with these goals.

Tests applied for the purpose of updating knowledge and methods of action are applied both as part of homework (or as a whole, covering homework), and in connection with determining the level of learning of the previous topic by students, and also at the first (initial) stage of mastering new material, and this has an effective effect on the results of training. Also, different levels of incorporating new knowledge and methods of action into previous experience can be covered in tasks (at the same time in tests), which serves to solve most of the tasks set before the educational process [10].

It is worth emphasizing that it is possible to benefit from tests in the application of all types of independent work, which are considered as carriers of new quality (let's not forget that when the opportunity becomes an action, a new quality is formed. See: [5]). However, it would be wrong to talk about an effective learning process outside of independent work. When we base this argument on this, we mean an independent work system and its nomenclature, which functions as a carrier of new quality, which realizes the possibilities of this process, in accordance with the logic of the learning

process, and we consider it a correct approach to understand independent work as a subsystem of the activity of the student (the learner, who is the subject of the goal of mastering the necessary part of human experience in a general education school), who acts as the main component (participating in the system) in the learning process. In our opinion, in the learning process, the subsystem of his activity, characterized by the fulfillment of the teacher's task without direct assistance, corresponding to the degree of independence of the student, is his independent work. (For more information, see [7]).

Here, let us illustrate our point by presenting two versions of test samples of this type (selected as a means of independent activity for students to actualize their past experience and incorporate new knowledge and methods of action into their experience).

After studying the material on "Planimetry Axioms" included in the "Geometry Content Line", students (in general schools, "students" and "students" are used as synonymous concepts - FN, KS) can use the tests below (as independent work) to study, apply, and strengthen the level of development of their knowledge, skills, and habits.

Option I

1. Points A, B, and C lie on a straight line. Segment BC is 3 times longer than segment AC. Segment AB is 3.6 cm shorter than segment BC. Find the length of segment AC.

- A) 2.4 cm B) 3.6 cm C) 1.2 cm D) 10.8 cm

2. The angle between rays m and c is 157° . The angle between rays n and c is 39° greater than the angle between rays m and n. If ray n passes between rays m and c, find $\angle(nc)$. The angle between the rays and is .

- A) 98° ; B) 108° ; C) 54° ; D) 59° .

3. Five points are marked on a plane: A,B,C,D,E. A straight line m divides this plane into two half-planes such that three of the marked points lie in one of these half-planes and two in the other. How many times can the broken straight line ABCDE intersect the straight line m?

- A) 1,3,5 times; B) 1,2,3,4,5 times; C) 1,2,3,4 times; D) does not cut.

4. How many triangles are there that are equal to the given triangle and whose two vertices coincide with the two vertices of this triangle that lie on the straight line β ? (Figure 1)

Figure 1.

- A) 1; B) 2; C) 3; D) 4.

5. Points K, P and M lie on a straight line and $MK=5.4$ cm, $KP=8$ cm. Find the length of the straight line segment MP.

- A) 2,6 cm; B) 13,4cm C) 2,6 cm and 13,4cm; D) 5,4 cm.

6. Six points are marked on a straight line: A, B, C, D, E, F. How many straight line segments are there whose endpoints are the given points?

- A) 10; B) 5; C) 15; D) 12.

7. Into how many parts can three different straight lines divide a plane?

- A) 4,5,6 parts; B) 4,6,7 parts; C) 4,5,6,7 parts; D) 3,4,5,6 parts. [6; p.17]

Option II

1. Points C, D, and E lie on a straight line. Segment DE is twice as short as segment CD. Segment CD is 4.8 cm shorter than segment CE. Find the length of segment DE. Points C, D and E lie on a straight line.

- A) 2.4 cm; B) 9.6 cm C) 4.8 cm D) 3.2 cm

2. The angle between rays a and b is 143° . The angle between rays a and c is 29° smaller than the angle between rays b and c. If ray c passes between rays a and b, find $\angle(bc)$.

- A) 59° ; B) 114° ; C) 57° ; D) 86° .

3. Four points are marked on the plane: M, N, P, K. The straight line ρ divides this plane into two half-planes such that two of the marked points lie in one of these half-planes and two in the other. How many times can the broken straight line MNPK intersect the straight line ρ ?

- A) 1, 2; B) 1, 2, 3; C) 1, 2, 3, 4; D) 2, 3.

4. How many triangles are there that are equal to the given triangle and whose two vertices coincide with the two vertices of this triangle that lie on the straight line ρ ? (Figure 3)

Figure 3

- A) 4; B) 2; C) 1; D) 3.

5. Points B, C and D lie on a straight line and $BC=9$ cm, $CD=6.7$ cm. Find the length of the straight line segment BD.

- A) 2.3 cm B) 15,7cm C) 2.3 cm and 15.7 cm D) 6.7 cm

6. How many straight lines are there that pass through two of the six given points, no three of which lie on the same straight line?

- A) 15; B) 12; C) 6; D) 30.

7. Into how many parts can four different straight lines divide a plane?

- A) 9; B) 10; C) 11; D) 12.

These tests can be used for another purpose, namely, to help students acquire new knowledge, specifically, to actualize the necessary experience for familiarization with the axioms of stereometry contained in the "Geometry content line". It is best to present these tests to students as homework before teaching "Axioms of Stereometry" and begin the lesson with an analysis of the results of that task, that is, the process of checking the homework should coincide with the actualization process.

In order to integrate new knowledge and methods of action into past experience and turn them into a system, generalization tests, which cover both individual topics and entire titles (teaching units, chapters), play an important role in realizing the capabilities of students in secondary schools. The following is an example of such tests - in order to integrate the knowledge, skills and habits acquired in the teaching of the topic "Reduction of Fractions" into the student's existing experience and turn them into a system, tests can be applied as independent work material in two versions.

1. At what value of x does the fraction $\frac{x-2}{x^2+4}$ become zero?

- A) $x = 4$; B) $x = 3$; C) $x = 2$; D) $x = -2$; E) $x = 0$.

2. Find the possible values of the variable x in the fraction $\frac{6x+7}{1,8-x}$

- A) $x = 1,8$; B) $x \neq 1,8$; C) $x \neq 2$; D) $x = 0$; E) $x = -\frac{7}{6}$

3. Find the possible values of the variables in the expression. $\frac{a}{a-b} - \frac{b}{a+b}$

- A) $a \neq b$; B) $a \neq -b$; C) $a = b$; D) $a = -b$; E) $a \neq \pm b$.

4. Find the possible values of the variables in the expression. $\left(\frac{a}{a^2-ab} - \frac{b}{b^2-ab}\right) : (a+b)$

- A) $a \neq 0, b \neq 0$; B) $a \neq 0, a \neq b$; C) $a \neq \pm b$;

- D) $a \neq 0, b \neq 0, a \neq \pm b$; E) $a \neq \pm b, a \neq 0$.

5. Which of the following equations is equivalent to the fraction $\frac{a}{b}$? $-\frac{a}{b}$; $-\frac{a}{-b}$; $-\frac{a}{b} - \frac{a}{-b}$; $-\frac{-a}{-b}$ ($a \neq 0, b \neq 0$)?

- A) 4; B) 2; C) 3; D) 5; E) 6.

6. Which of the following fractions is equivalent to the fraction $\frac{a-b-c}{a+b-c}$

$$\frac{b+c-a}{c-b-a}; \frac{b+c-a}{a+b-c}; -\frac{b+c-a}{a+b-c}; -\frac{b+c-a}{c-b-a}; -\frac{b+c-a}{c+b-c}?$$

- A) 1; B) 2; C) 3; D) 4; E) none.

7. If a, b, c, d are consecutive even natural numbers, calculate the value of the expression $\frac{b-a}{c-b}$

- A) 2; B) 3; C) 4; D) 1; E) 5.

8. Reduce the fraction: $\frac{3a-3}{a^2-1}$

- A) $\frac{3}{a-1}$; B) $\frac{3}{a+1}$; C) $\frac{3a}{a-1}$; D) $\frac{3a}{a-1}$; E) $\frac{a-1}{3}$.

9. Reduce the fraction: $\frac{9-6x+x^2}{x^2-9}$

- A) $\frac{3-x}{x+3}$; B) $\frac{x+3}{x-3}$; C) $\frac{x-3}{x+3}$; D) $\frac{x+3}{3-x}$; E) $\frac{x+3}{x-9}$

10. Reduce the fraction: $\frac{(a^2-1)^2+4a^2}{a^4-1}$

- A) -1; B) $\frac{5a^2-1}{a^2+1}$; C) $\frac{a^2+1}{a^2-1}$; D) $\frac{5a^2-1}{a^2+1}$; E) $\frac{a^4+1}{a^4-1}$.

11. If $a^2 = 40 + b$ and $b^2 = 8 + a$ and, find the value of the expression. $\frac{a^2-ab-a^2b+b^2}{ab^2-a^2-b^2+ab}$

- A) 1; B) 2; C) -2; D) 5; E) -5.

12. Reduce the fraction: $\frac{(m-1)^3-8}{3m^2-18m+27}$

- 13 A) $\frac{m^2-3}{m-3}$; B) $\frac{m^2+3}{3(m-3)}$; C) $\frac{m^2+3}{3}$; D) $\frac{3}{m^2+3}$; E) $\frac{m^2+3}{m-3}$.

13. Reduce the fraction: $\frac{b^{45}+1}{b^3-b^{18}+b^{33}}$
 A) $\frac{b^{15}+1}{b^3}$; B) $\frac{b^{30}+1}{b^3}$; C) $\frac{b^{15}+1}{b^6}$; D) $\frac{b^{30}+1}{b^6}$; E) $\frac{b^{15}+1}{b^9}$. [4; s. 61-71]

The following are examples of final tests applied at the end of the teaching work on "Expressions with Variables", "Linear Function", "Force", "Properties of Force", and "Operations on Polynomials" (two examples of variants).

Option I

- Calculate the value of the expression if $a = 6, b = -11, c = -10b^2 - 4bc$
 A) 452; B) -202; C) -404; D) 476.
- Calculate the value of the expression if $x = -0,8$;
 $-0,5(3x - 4) - 1,5(6 + 5x)$
 A) -0.4; B) 0.2; C) 0.4; D) -0.2.
- Solve the equation. $5 - 2(3x - 4) = 4x - 3$
 A) 1.6; B) -1.6; C) $\frac{5}{8}$; D) $-\frac{5}{8}$.
- Two typists typed a 97-page manuscript. The first typist worked for 4 hours and the second typist for 5 hours. If the two typists together typed 22 pages per hour, how many pages did the second typist type in 1 hour?
 A) 14 pages; B) 13 pages; C) 9 pages; D) 8 pages.
- Simplify the expression. $\frac{(-1,5x^2y)^3(2y^3)^4}{(6x^3y^2)^2}$
 A) $-1,5x^4y^{11}$; B) $-2,5x^4y^{11}$; C) $-1,5x^6y^{11}$; D) $-1,5x^4y^8$.
- Solve the equation. $\frac{2x-3}{4} - \frac{5x+2}{6} = 3$
 A) $-\frac{4}{49}$; B) -12,25; C) -11,5; D) 12,25.
- Simplify the expression. $(3x - 2)(2x - 1) - (5x + 2)(3x - 4)$
 A) $-9x^2 + 7x - 10$; B) $-9x^2 - 7x + 10$; C) $-9x^2 + 7x + 10$; D) $-9x^2 - 7x - 10$.
- The graph of the function $y=x/3+2$ intersects the abscissa at (m;0) and the ordinate at (0;n). Find the sum of m+n.
 A) 6; B) 4; C) -2; D) -4.
- The gardener walked from the garden to the shop along the village road at a speed of 5 km/h, and returned along the forest road at a speed of 3 km/h. He spent 8 minutes less time returning. The forest road is 2 km shorter than the village road. Find the distance the gardener traveled.
 A) 12 km; B) 6 km; C) 8 km; D) 10 km.

Option II

- Calculate the value of the expression if
 $a = 7, b = -8, c = -12b^2 - 4bc$
 A) 413; B) -370; C) -433; D) -335.
- Calculate the value of the expression if $x = -\frac{2}{3}$
 $-2,5(4x = 3) - 0,5(5 - 2x)$
 A) -4; B) -2; C) -3; D) -4.5.
- Solve the equation. $3 - 4(2x - 5) = 2 - 6x$
 A) $\frac{2}{21}$; B) 8,5; C) 10,5; D) 12.
- Two stamping machines produced 188 parts. The first machine worked for 6 hours and the second machine for 4 hours. If the two machines produced 39 parts in 1 hour, how many parts can be produced in 1 hour on the second machine?
 A) 18; B) 21; C) 16; D) 23.
- Simplify the expression. $\frac{(-0,5y^3x)^2(2x^2y)^3}{(\frac{1}{3}x^5y^3)^2}$
 A) $\frac{18y^3}{x^2}$; B) $\frac{9y^3}{x^2}$; C) $\frac{18y^2}{x^2}$; D) $\frac{18y^3}{x}$.
- Solve the equation. $\frac{3x-1}{6} - \frac{2x+3}{8} = 2$
 A) $\frac{6}{61}$; B) $10\frac{1}{6}$; C) $-10\frac{1}{6}$; D) $10\frac{1}{3}$.
- Simplify the expression. $(4x - 3)(3x + 2) - (1 - 2x)(5 - 3x)$
 A) $6x^2 + 12x + 11$; B) $-6x^2 - 12x + 11$; C) $6x^2 - 12x - 11$; D) $6x^2 + 12x - 11$.
- The graph of the function $y=-1.5x-2$ intersects the abscissa at (a;0) and the ordinate at (0;b). Find the sum of a+b.
 A) -2; B) $-2\frac{1}{3}$; C) $-3\frac{1}{3}$; D) -2,5.
- A pedestrian walked to the forest at a speed of 4 km/h through the countryside, and returned at a speed of 3 km/h along the highway. It took him 45 minutes longer to get back. The highway is 2 km longer than the countryside road. Find the distance the pedestrian traveled
 A) 4 km; B) 6 km; C) 8 km; D) 10 km. [2; 19-20]

Through the processing of the information obtained during the research process, it was concluded that when selecting test tasks as a means of organizing students' learning activities, especially their independent work, it would be useful to anticipate the following psycho-didactic requirements:

* Test tasks should be selected and systematized based on the tasks ahead. The system of applied test tasks should include two important aspects:

1) The general goal of the educational process: a) the logic of assimilating the experience that humanity has acquired in the process of its historical development; b) the practice of preserving what has been achieved; c) the method of orientation towards the preparation for the acquisition of creative experience necessary for the civilization and freedom of man and the society to which he belongs; d) the norms of orientation towards the acquisition of qualities that condition the coexistence of people, which are organically connected with the previous three goals, and the opening of the window to the world for him;

2) Transforming the training process into a well-managed process.

It is necessary to determine the point of application of the test in the learning process and the form of coverage of students. In our opinion, test tasks can be applied at all stages of the learning process: a) during the justification of learning and updating of past experience; b) during the acquisition of knowledge; c) during the application and systematization of knowledge, skills and habits; d) during the assessment of the process and results by the teacher and the student himself. According to the form of coverage of students: individual; pair; group; frontal.*

The duration of the test tasks, their coverage of previous knowledge, the level of difficulty of the new tasks to be determined, and their suitability for the student's potential should be determined.*

The teacher should consider the type and form of the test task; the conditions and requirements of the task should be clear; the student should be given necessary and clarifying instructions for their activity.*

Consistency, systematicity, students' cognitive development style, dynamics, its stages, individual and age characteristics should be taken into account in the application of test tasks.*

It is important to include enabling moments and new elements in test tasks for generalization, systematization, and application of knowledge in a changed situation; the implementation of tasks should be based on the students' acquired knowledge, habits and skills, life experiences, and observations, and the student should be directed towards acquiring more general knowledge, skills, habits, and experience.*

Test tasks should, with their content, fun, and logic, create and develop the student's interest in learning.*

Test tasks should encourage the formation of the student's ability to make accurate and fair assessments, which is considered one of the most important personal qualities.*

The system of test tasks should maintain the unity of mental and practical activity. During the execution of test tasks, the working conditions should be improved with the correct guidance of the teacher in order to develop the analytical and heuristic aspects of the student's mental activity in unity, to form his own activity as a subject of management. The teacher should continuously adjust the management work in accordance with specific conditions. [5; 58-59]*

Scientific novelty of the research. The research work identified psycho-didactic requirements that should be considered when formulating test tasks as a means of organizing students' learning activities, especially their independent work.

Practical significance of the research. Determining the psycho-didactic requirements that must be observed when formulating test tasks as a means of organizing students' learning activities, especially their independent work, will play a positive role in eliminating errors made in the activities of practical educators.

Result. When applying test tasks as a means of organizing and managing students' learning activities, especially their independent work, it is possible to positively influence (improve) the quality of the learning process by meeting psycho-didactic requirements.

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